

WEBSITES AND PAGES FOR CREATING VIRTUAL BIOLOGY LABORATORIES**Turakulova M.***Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov***Ruzikulova N.***Samarkand State Medical University***Abstract**

The article presents information about the role of information technology (IT) in the teaching of biological science using the example of virtual laboratories. The integration of information technology (IT) in modern education has revolutionized pedagogical approaches, especially in the field of science education. Through a mixed-methods research design that includes both quantitative evaluation and qualitative research, this study aims to shed light on the effectiveness and implications of virtual laboratories in biology education. The use of virtual laboratories in various educational settings leads to a comprehensive development of the impact on students' learning outcomes, activity and perception. The integration of virtual laboratories in the field of biological sciences has allowed students to learn and engage with complex concepts.

Keywords: information technology (IT), biology, education, web pages, virtual laboratory, online, pedagogy, Front-End.

Traditionally, the study of biology has relied heavily on hands-on laboratory experiences to reinforce theoretical knowledge and develop practical skills. However, logistical constraints, limited resources, and safety issues often present significant challenges in providing comprehensive laboratory experiences for all students. In such situations, the use of virtual laboratories gives high results.

According to N. Azizah, S. Aloysius[7], the relationship between the level of education and virtual laboratory tools in the study of biology, the suitability of virtual laboratory tools used by students to achieve maximum educational goals is very important because R.A. According to Desharnais and P. Narguizian [8], another advantage of virtual laboratories is that they can be used to overcome the limitations associated with the high resource requirements of conventional laboratories. In addition, A. A. N. Alshaikh [1] in his scientific works on virtual laboratories put forward ideas that the student's laboratory skills can be improved by using a virtual teaching and learning environment called "virtual laboratory".

One of the most important advantages of virtual laboratories is their ability to democratize access to high-quality educational resources. Using digital platforms, students from diverse backgrounds and geographic locations can simultaneously engage in immersive learning experiences reserved for privileged institutions. Virtual labs facilitate active learning by providing students with opportunities to explore, experiment, and solve problems in a risk-free environment. Through interactive simulations and multimedia resources, students can manipulate variables, observe results in real time, and deepen their understanding of biological concepts. This practical approach not only strengthens theoretical knowledge, but also develops critical thinking and scientific inquiry. In addition, virtual labs offer unprecedented flexibility and scalability, allowing educators to tailor the learning experience to meet the diverse needs and learning styles of students. Whether integrated into traditional classrooms, blended learning environments, or fully online courses, virtual labs can fit a wide range of learning approaches and

learning objectives. Additionally, the asynchronous nature of virtual labs allows students to engage with course material at their own pace, which promotes self-direction and autonomy. Beyond the classroom, virtual labs also hold promise for research and innovation. By providing researchers with virtual platforms to model biological phenomena, test hypotheses, and analyze data, virtual laboratories accelerate the pace of discovery and facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration. According to T.Lynch, I.Ghergulescular[9], from a technological point of view, the inclusion of virtual laboratories in the educational process often requires adjustment or expansion of existing resources available in laboratories.

Methodology. Virtual experiments, that is, interactive laboratory work, can be carried out on online resources or through a number of special disks. Our research is based on the creation of virtual laboratories conducted in secondary schools based on online resources, in which the selection of virtual laboratory platforms and activity design methods were used to create laboratories.

In the selection of virtual laboratory platforms, criteria such as simulation realism, interactivity, usability and compatibility with different devices were taken into account to ensure the suitability of the platforms for various educational conditions and general education school students. Activity design involves designing learning activities and experiences that take advantage of these platforms to increase student engagement and understanding of biological concepts. Based on pedagogical principles and instructional design best practices, a series of interactive simulations, virtual dissections, data analysis exercises, and collaborative projects were developed to address various topics within the biological sciences curriculum.

Research results and discussion. To create virtual laboratories, the Front-End field of programming in computer technologies was taken as a basis. That is, this field is focused on creating web pages, and we learned to create virtual laboratories that are conducted online. One of the most convenient programs for working in the field of Front-End is Visual Studio Code, which includes 3 different programming languages:

a) HTML (hypertext markup language) is the basis of web pages and is used to create the content of web pages. HTML is a type of programming that mainly uses tags. These tags make it possible to place texts, tables, various information, pictures, songs, videos, audios, which are the basis of the web page (Fig. 1).

```

1 <!DOCTYPE html>
2 <html lang="en">
3 <head>
4   <meta charset="UTF-8">
5   <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
6   <title>Document</title>
7   <link rel="stylesheet" href="style.css">
8 </head>
9 <body>
10
11   <div class="head">
12     <div><h1>biologiya fanidan virtual laboratoriyalar</h1></div>
13     <div></div>
14   </div>
15
16   <div class="container_cart">
17     <div class="top">
18       <a href="5-sinf/6-sinf.html">
19         
20         <h2>5-sinf</h2>
21       </a>
22     </div>
23     <div>
24       <a href="7-sinf/7-sinf.html">
25         
26         <h2>7-sinf</h2>
27       </a>
28     </div>
29     <div>
30       <a href="8-sinf/8-sinf.html">
31         
32         <h2>8-sinf</h2>
33       </a>
34     </div>
35   </div>
36 </body>
37 </html>

```

Figure 1. A window of Visual Studio Code in HTML.

b) CSS- (Cascading style sheets) is used to control the layout and visual presentation of web pages. Using CSS, you can design the information written in HTML, change their color, shape, and type (Fig. 2).

```

1
2   margin: 0;
3   padding: 0;
4   box-sizing: border-box;
5 }
6
7 .image {
8   text-align: center;
9   margin-top: 30px;
10 }
11
12 .container {
13   display: grid;
14   grid-template-columns: repeat(auto-fit, minmax(220px,1fr));
15   gap: 20px;
16   padding: 30px;
17 }
18
19 .container > div {
20   margin-top: 40px;
21   border: 1px solid #e3e3e3;
22   border-radius: 70px;
23   padding: 30px;
24   background-color: #white;
25   cursor: pointer;
26   text-align: center;
27 }
28
29 .container img {
30   width: 100px;
31   height: 100px;
32   margin-top: 20px;
33   /* border-radius: 50px; */
34 }
35
36 .container a,h3 {
37   text-decoration: none;
38   text-align: center;
39   padding: 20px 0;
40   color: #cadetblue;
41 }
42
43 .container h1 {

```

Figure 2. Visual Studio Code CSS window.

c) JavaScript is a versatile programming language used to add interactivity and functionality to web pages (Figure 3).

Figure 3. A JavaScript popup in Visual Studio Code.

Virtual labs offer unprecedented flexibility and scalability, allowing educators to tailor the learning experience to meet the diverse needs and learning styles of students. Whether integrated into traditional classrooms, blended learning environments, or fully online courses, virtual labs can fit a wide range of learning approaches and learning objectives. Additionally, the asynchronous nature of virtual labs allows students to

engage with course material at their own pace, which promotes self-direction and autonomy. Based on the following methodology, a virtual project of laboratories for biology of general education schools was partially created. According to it, the biology textbooks created for the 5th, 7th, 8th and 9th grades of secondary schools were taken as a basis (pictures 4-5-6-7-8).

Figure 4. Homepage of the website.

127.0.0.1:5500/5-3-laboratory/5-3.html

Figure 5. The page of the website with the name of the topics of the labs in 5th grade biology.

Figure 6. The page of the website with the name of the topics of laboratories in 7th grade biology.

Figure 7. The page of the website with the name of the topics of the labs in 8th grade biology

Figure 8. The page of the website with the name of the topics of laboratories in biology of the 9th grade.

Virtual laboratories, despite their advantages, present a number of challenges. The reliability of processes compared to real experiments is one of the main problems. Although virtual environments strive to replicate real laboratory experiences, tactile interaction and self-problem solving may be lacking, which may limit the development of hands-on skills. In addition, the initial investment required to develop high-quality virtual labs and ensure the compatibility of technological infrastructure can present some challenges for educational institutions, especially those with limited financial resources. Also, the integration of virtual laboratories into biology curricula requires adequate training and support of teachers. Teachers must be proficient in managing these digital tools to effectively guide student learning and facilitate meaningful interactions. In addition, it is important to constantly update and maintain virtual laboratories to ensure that they are in line with current scientific advances and educational standards.

Virtual labs are a transformative tool in biology education, leveraging IT to improve accessibility, flexibility, and experiential learning. While challenges remain, ongoing progress and collaborative efforts will evolve to further optimize these digital resources and expand their impact on student learning and engagement.

In conclusion, it can be said that the integration of virtual laboratories represents a revolutionary paradigm shift in biology education, improves educational outcomes, promotes inclusiveness, and enables the development of scientific research. Virtual labs offer students an immersive and interactive learning environment, demonstrating the ability to simulate real science experiments. By harnessing the power of digital platforms, educators can create immersive learning experiences that allow students to explore the wonders of biology and prepare them for the challenges of the 21st century.

References

1. Asma Abdulrahman Nami Alshaikh // The Reality of Using Virtual Labs in Teaching Advanced Biology Curricula in Developing Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) among Female Teachers at Secondary Level in Al-Kharj // Hindawi // Volume 20. Pages 1-12. London-2022.
2. Javlon Abdullo // Perfect programming 1: HTML va CSS // Akademnashr // Tashkent-2021 // Pages 288.
3. Javlon Abdullo // Perfect programming 2: JavaScript // Akademnashr // Tashkent-2021. Pages 300.
4. Marc Lancer Santos, Maricar Prudente // Effectiveness of Virtual Laboratories in Science Education: A Meta-Analysis // International Journal of Information and Education Technology // Volume 12. №2 // Pages 150-156 // Singapore-2022.
5. Moges Abebe and others // Implementation of Virtual Laboratory Platform to Study Human Buffer Solutions in the Era of COVID-19 // Educational Research Applications // Volume 5. Issue 04 // Pages 1-5 // USA-2020 //
6. Mohamed Elsayed Ahmed, Shinobu Hasegawa // Development of Online Virtual Laboratory Platform for Supporting Real Laboratory Experiments in Multi Domains // Education sciences. №10. Pages 1-14. Basel-2021.
7. Nurul Azizah, Aloysius S // The Effects of Virtual Laboratory on Biology Learning Achievement: A Literature Review // Atlantis press. №15. Pages 107-116. France-2020.
8. Robert A. Desharnais, Pol Narguizian // Virtual labs for GE biology // Course redesign with technology. №5. Pages 1-15. California-2014.
9. Tiina Lynch, Ioana Ghergulescu // Review of virtual labs as the emerging technologies for teaching STEM subjects // Research and innovation. Surabaya-2020. 2-3 pages.
10. Yuli Wahyuni, Rofi'Y, Yoso Wiyarno // The development of a virtual laboratory as a virus learning media to improve student learning outcomes in biology subjects // International journal of social science and

human research. Volume 5. Issue 2. Pages 600-604. USA-2022.

11. Turakulova M.N // Advantages of using computer tools as pedagogical tools in biology laboratories // International scientific and practical conference "The new uzbekistan creator of spiritually perfect youths". Uzbekistan-2024. Pages 776-779.

12. Turakulova M.N., Ruzikulova N.A. // The importance of virtual laboratories in science and the types of programming used in their creation //Current problems of science and education in the context of modern

challenges (MKAP-27). Moscow-2024. Pages 180-183.

13. Turakulova M., Ruzikulova N. The significance of didactic games in assessing students'knowledge //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. B3. – C. 65-67.

14. Turakulova M.N. Organizing virtual laboratories in biology for high schools by creating websites //Education and innovative research 2024 y. № 6. Pages 251-257.